

Status	Errors	Channel Settings	Serial Settings	Sequence	Script						
#	Name	Mode	Rate (Hz)	Min	Max	On startup or error:	Speed	Acceleration	8-bit neutral	8-bit range (+/-)	
0	Laser 1 Power	Output		992	2000	Off	992,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
1	Laser 1 Power	Output		992	2000	Off	992,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
2	Laser 2	Output		992	2000	Off	992,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
3	na	Input		0	256	Ignore	0,00	0	0	256,00	476,25
4	Laser 2 Power	Output		992	2000	Off	992,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
5	Laser 2 Power	Output		992	2000	Off	992,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
6	Laser 1	Output		992	2000	Off	992,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
7	Laser 2 X Achse	Servo	50	992	2000	Off	992,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
8	Laser 2 Y Achse	Servo	50	992	1712	Off	992,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
9	Laser 1 Y Achse	Servo	50	1456	1664	Off	1456,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
10	Laser 1 X Achse	Servo	50	1040	2000	Off	1040,00	0	0	1500,00	476,25
11	na	Input		0	256	Ignore	0,00	0	0	256,00	476,25

Advanced Pulse Control

Period (ms):

Period multiplier:

Figure S1: Channel settings for a two kinematic setup. "Laser 1 or 2 Power" (#0&1 or #4&5) switches the servos on/off. Laser 1 or 2 (#2 or #6) switches the pointer on/off. Laser 1/2 X/Y Achse controls the servos representing the corresponding axis. na: not available are unused positions.

Connected to: #00323076 Firmware version: 1.02

Status	Errors	Channel Settings	Serial Settings	Sequence	Script		
#	Name	Mode	Enabled	Target	Speed	Acceleration	Position
0	Laser 1 Power	Output	<input type="checkbox"/>		1500,00	0	0,00
1	Laser 1 Power	Output	<input type="checkbox"/>		1500,00	0	0,00
2	Laser 2	Output	<input type="checkbox"/>		1500,00	0	0,00
3	na	Input	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		0,00	0	0,00
4	Laser 2 Power	Output	<input type="checkbox"/>		1500,00	0	0,00
5	Laser 2 Power	Output	<input type="checkbox"/>		1500,00	0	0,00
6	Laser 1	Output	<input type="checkbox"/>		1500,00	0	0,00
7	Laser 2 X	Servo	<input type="checkbox"/>		1500,00	0	0,00
8	Laser 2 Y	Servo	<input type="checkbox"/>		1352,00	0	0,00
9	Laser 1 Y	Servo	<input type="checkbox"/>		1535,00	0	0,00
10	Laser 1 X	Servo	<input type="checkbox"/>		1575,75	0	0,00
11	na	Input	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		0,00	0	0,00

PWM Output

Enable PWM on channel 8

On time: Units: 1/48 μs

Period: (20.8 ns)

Figure S2: After the settings have been defined in "Channel Settings" (Fig. S1) and the controller is put into "live"-mode by clicking "Play Sequence" in the Sequence-tab (blue rectangle), this Status tab can be used to train the laser on the position to be taught. This should be finished by